

Equilibrium Studies of Protonation of Dye Base in Benzene

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Received 13 July 1972

The equilibrium of the interaction between carbinol base of crystal violet and aromatic acids in benzene medium has been investigated spectrophotometrically at 6.5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35°. The absorption spectra and extinction coefficient ($\epsilon = 8.67 \times 10^4$ lit. mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹) of the coloured form of carbinol base of crystal violet in benzene have been determined. The experimental results fit a formula of the type

$$K_a = \frac{(\text{Salt})}{(\text{Carbinol Base})(\text{acid})^n},$$

the value of 'n' varies from acid to acid and has always a non-integral value greater than unity. It has been suggested that the presence of various associated forms of acid molecules such as acid-anion complexes in benzene might provide a plausible explanation for the enhanced acidity of the acids and also for the non-integral value of 'n'. The values of K_a and 'n' decrease with rise in temperature pointing to a decrease in the association of the acid-anion complex. A fairly linear relationship has been obtained for the above acids when log K_a values for different acids in benzene have been plotted against the corresponding pKa values in water.

Few systematic investigations on acid-base equilibria in aprotic solvents using indicator dyes as reference acids or bases have so far been reported¹⁻¹¹. The main difficulty arises out of the insolubility of most dyes in benzene and other aprotic solvents. This difficulty can be easily got over by converting the dye into its basic form and extracting it in benzene, a technique first introduced by Palit^{12,13}. We have utilised the above method in the present spectrophotometric investigation on the interaction between aromatic acids and a reference base e.g. carbinol base of crystal violet in aprotic media, mainly benzene.

Materials and Method

The solvents (benzene, toluene and xylene) were purified by standard methods and stored over sodium wire. The acids, benzoic (Bayer Leverkusen); salicylic (Rhodesia), *m*- and *p*-nitro benzoic (Fluka) and other substituted acids (Eastern Kodak Co.) were of extra pure quality; some of them were recrystallized and were heated to about 50° in vacuum oven to remove residual solvent. Fresh solutions of vacuum-dried samples in dry benzene were immediately used. Crystal Violet (E. Merck) was recrystallized twice from methanol-benzene mixture and dried in vacuum.

Preparation of Carbinol Base : About 10 to 12 mg of crystal violet dye was dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water and was precipitated as carbinol base by adding 10 ml of 2 *N* sodium hydroxide solution. The precipitated dye was then extracted with about 200 ml

of benzene and the benzene extract (which slowly changes from yellow to the stable colourless carbinol form within 24 hr) was stored over sodium wire in an air-tight pyrex glass container.

Experimental Procedure : The colourless carbinol base of crystal violet in benzene slowly reacts with acids to produce a coloured salt. The extent of formation of coloured salt with various acids was measured spectrophotometrically. The acid solutions were prepared gravimetrically and all the optical measurements were recorded from Hilger UVSPECK spectrophotometer using 1 cm stoppered silica cells, whose temperature was maintained constant within $\pm 0.1^\circ$ by circulating water through the cell holder by a special device. The condensation of moisture on cell window below 20° was removed by placing phosphorous pentoxide in the cell compartment. Error due to absorption of dye on the cell surface was avoided by 'plating' with dye both the sample and the reference cells before the commencement of the actual measurements. Fig. 1 is absorption spectra of crystal violet in different solvents, showing the spectral maxima of coloured salt in benzene at 610 nm. All the optical measurements in benzene medium were recorded at spectra maximum, 610 nm.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of crystal violet in different solvents at 25° .

1. $7.51 \times 10^{-6}M$ Crystal Violet in Water.
2. $7.46 \times 10^{-6}M$ Crystal Violet in Aqueous H_2SO_4 ($3.0 \times 10^{-3}M$) solution.
3. In benzene ($3.30 \times 10^{-6}M$ Crystal Violet).
4. In toluene—colour of carbinol base developed by $1.26 \times 10^{-3}M$ Salicylic acid.
5. In xylene—colour of carbinol base developed by $7.82 \times 10^{-4}M$ Salicylic acid.

Method of Calculation : The indicator ratio $[\text{BH}^+\text{A}^-]/[\text{B}]$ is calculated graphically from the ratio $(x_e)/[(b)-(x_e)]$ where (b) is initial concentration of carbinol base expressed in terms of optical density (O.D.) and (x_e) is the concentration of the coloured salt at equilibrium in the same unit. The initial concentration of carbinol base can be determined by complete conversion of carbinol base into the coloured salt with such an excess of benzoic acid that further addition of the acid does not bring about any change in colour intensity. Benzoic acid was preferably chosen for such measurements because the spectral maximum of the coloured salt was found to be independent of the concentration of benzoic acid in the solution.

The total concentration of the indicator base in terms of molarity could be obtained by partition method¹⁰. The total amount of dye present in benzene layer could be extracted into aqueous layer by shaking the carbinol base repeatedly with a aqueous sulphuric acid solution ($3 \times 10^{-3} N$). After making up the solution to a suitable volume, the O.D. could be measured and the concentration determined from Beer's law relationship (Fig. 2). Any intermediate O.D. reading could be converted into the molar concentration from the extinction coefficient ($\epsilon = 8.67 \times 10^4$ litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹) of crystal violet in benzene at 25°.

Fig. 2. Beer's Law of Crystal Violet in aqueous H_2SO_4 ($3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) at $\lambda_{max} = 595 \text{ nm}$ (25°).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is well known¹⁴ that the carbinol base of crystal violet $(\text{NMe}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_3 \cdot \text{C} \cdot \text{OH}$, reacts with acids slowly with the loss of water molecule to produce the dye cation which has the structure

The cation can react slowly with hydroxyl ions to reform the carbinol base. Most probably the water molecule formed remains associated with any one of the species present in the system through hydrogen bonding and they exist together as one entity^{15,16}. The reaction between carbinol base of crystal violet and an acid may thus be represented as

and for simplicity we write the above equilibrium as

where B represents the base, HA stands for the acid and BH^+A^- represents the coloured salt. Hence the association constant K_a is given by

$$K_a = \frac{[\text{BH}^+\text{A}^-]}{[\text{B}][\text{HA}]} \quad (3)$$

A set of typical experimental results is shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Values of the Ratio (Coloured form)/(Colourless form) at fixed Acid Concentration and Different Base Concentrations

Salicylic acid concentration = $4.753 \times 10^{-5} M$; Temp. = $20 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Carbinol base conc. $\times 10^6 M$	<i>b</i>	<i>x_e</i>	$\frac{(\text{Coloured form})}{(\text{Colourless form})} = \frac{[\text{BH}^+\text{A}^-]}{[\text{B}]}$
18.65	1.617	0.953	1.435
14.75	1.279	0.762	1.474
11.02	0.955	0.568	1.468
7.209	0.625	0.376	1.510

TABLE 2

Values of Exponent 'n' at Different Temperatures

Acid	pK _a	Exponent 'n' at temperature						
		25°	6.5°	10°	15°	20°	25°	30°
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic	3.82	2.68	2.53	2.36	2.27	2.19	—	—
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic	3.40	2.69	2.53	2.38	2.26	2.15	—	—
<i>m</i> -Toluic	4.28	2.89	2.60	2.56	2.48	2.41	—	—
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic	3.46	3.61	3.47	3.19	2.62	2.25	—	—
Benzoic	4.17	—	—	—	2.40	2.17	2.07	1.86
Salicylic	3.00	—	—	—	2.12	2.06	2.00	1.56

It would be observed from Table 1 that equation (3) is obeyed within experimental error at a particular acid concentration; that is the values of K_a are constant when the carbinol base concentration is varied at a fixed concentration of the acid. However, when the acid concentration is varied the equation (3) no longer holds good and the value of K_a increases rapidly with the increase in acid concentration. This is clearly indicated by the fact that we do not get linear graphs with unit slope when $\log [BH^+A^-]/[B]$ is plotted against $-\log [HA]$ for different acids (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Plots of $\log[BH^+A^-]/[B]$ vs $-\log[HA]$ for the reaction between carbinol base and benzoic acid in benzene medium at different temperatures, 1. 20°; 2, 25°; 3, 30°; 4, 35°.

From this linear plot of Fig. 3 it is evident that our experimental results fit well with an empirical formula as given below

$$K_a = \frac{[BH^+A^-]}{[B][HA]^n} \quad (4)$$

where the value of 'n' varies from acid to acid. Similar expressions have been used by several workers^{1,10,11,17} in their investigation on dye-acid interaction in aprotic and other non-aqueous solvents. Equation (4) can be written as :

$$\log \frac{[BH^+A^-]}{[B]} - n \log [HA] = \log K_a \quad (5)$$

At 50% salt conversion, the value of $[BH^+A^-]/[B] = 1$, and hence

$$\log K_a = -n \log [HA] \text{ 50\% conversion} \quad (6)$$

According to equation (5) when $\log [\text{BH}^+\text{A}^-]/[\text{B}]$ is plotted against $-\log [\text{HA}]$, it should give a straight line graph with slope equal to 'n' and intercept equal to $\log K_a$. A typical graph showing such plottings for benzoic acid at different temperatures is shown in Fig. 3. Similar graphs are obtained for other acids. The values of 'n' are always greater than unity (Table 2). The values of $\log K_a$ can also be obtained by applying equation (6) and are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3
Values of $\log K_a$ at Different Temperatures

Acid	pKa in water 25°	log K_a at temperature						
		6.5°	10°	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic	3.82	9.41	8.67	7.96	7.49	7.01	—	—
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic	3.40	11.15	10.51	9.70	9.14	8.49	—	—
<i>m</i> -Toluic	4.28	6.12	5.42	5.30	4.95	4.72	—	—
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic	3.46	14.99	14.43	13.14	10.79	9.08	—	—
Benzoic	4.17	—	—	—	5.28	4.65	4.35	3.81
Salicylic	3.00	—	—	—	9.34	8.93	8.44	6.59

Comparison of Relative Strength of Acids : From the values of $\log K_a$ (Table 3), which can be taken as a measure of the strength of various acids in benzene medium, the most remarkable thing is that the K_a values in benzene spreads out over nearly six decades, whereas the K_a values in water ranges just over one decade. Evidently, there is strong leveling effect in water which tends to equalise the apparent strength of weak acids. It therefore seems that such experiments give a better scope of differentiating between the strengths of weak acids; *m*-Nitro-benzoic acid can be cited as an extreme example. It is about 5 times stronger than benzoic acid in H_2O , whereas it is well over 10^5 times in C_6H_6 . It is quite likely that the nitrogroup is so highly solvated in H_2O that its meso-meric effect is very much diminished. Salicylic acid which acts both as a carboxylic and phenolic acid, is only 17 times stronger than benzoic acid in water but it is about 10^4 times stronger in benzene. Such increased acidity may be due to intra-molecular hydrogen bonding which enhances the acidity of proton donor by putting the electron density away from carboxyl hydrogen atom and thus easing its departure¹⁸. Here also the solvation of the phenolic hydroxyl may be a barrier to intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

Comparison of $\log K_a$ in Benzene with pKa in Water : A fairly good straight line is obtained when the values of $\log K_a$ in benzene at 25° are plotted against corresponding pKa values in water at 25° (Fig. 4). Salicylic acid however falls somewhat below the line. However, it should be noted that the order of the relative strength of different acids in benzene with reference to the carbinol base of crystal violet is in some cases not exactly the same as their order in water as shown below for K_a values at 25°. (I is in benzene; II is in water).

- I *m*-Nitro > Salicylic > *p*-Nitro > *m*-Chloro > *m*-Toluic > Benzoic
 II Salicylic > *p*-Nitro > *m*-Nitro > *m*-Chloro > Benzoic > *m*-Toluic

Discussion on the Non-integral Value of 'n': It is seen from Table 2 that the value of exponent 'n' for different acids is non-integral and always greater than unity. Kolthoff and Bruckenstein^{10,20} made somewhat similar observations while studying dye-acid interaction in acetic acid medium. They explained the value of exponent 'n' less than unity by considering the partial dissociation of ion-pair IH^+X^- . But this idea of partial dissociation of salt or ion-pair in acidic medium is not applicable in benzene medium possessing very low dielectric constant⁴. Moreover self association of IH^+X^- or dye molecules is negligible in the concentration range we have worked^{4,21,22}.

It is well established that most of the carboxylic acids are associated in benzene near the concentration range we have worked. The dimerisation constant of benzoic acid²³ in benzene is 6.4×10^4 at 5.4° . If we assume that the associated acid molecules do not contribute to the acidity of the solution, then correction for association of acid molecules will only increase the value of 'n' from unity. Marryot²⁴ was first to account for the increase in the acidity exhibited by carboxylic acids in inert media on the basis of the presence of acid-anion complex in the solution. The conductometric²⁴, potentiometric²⁵, cryoscopic²⁶ and infrared^{27,28} studies established the presence of stable carboxyl-carboxylate ion complex in inert solvents. The fact that acid-anion complexes are likely to take part in the reactions was evident from the observations of Harlow and Bruss²⁵ that monobasic and phenolic acids in inert solvents like benzene often show two inflections during potentiometric titration; the steeper one being ascribed by them to acid-anion complex. Similarly Heijde²⁹ and Harlow²⁵ indicate that phenol exists as phenol-phenolate ion complex in the inert solvent. We can also extend similar arguments for explaining the greater acidity of the carboxylic acids in our system. Thus in the system the carboxylic acid exists as free

Fig. 4. Comparison of $\log K_a$ in benzene at 25° with $\text{p}K_a$ in water at 25° .
 1, *m*-chlorobenzoic acid; 2, *p*-nitrobenzoic acid; 3, *m*-toluic acid; 4, *m*-nitrobenzoic acid;
 5, benzoic acid; 6, salicylic acid.

carboxylic acid molecules, carboxylic-carboxylate ion complexes and the non-reactive associated acid molecules. We consider that the presence of three types of acid-species in the solution is responsible for the non-integral value of 'n'. Since the acid anion complex due to greater stability is stronger out of the two reaction species, the presence of such stable complexes accounts for making the value of 'n' greater than unity.

Effect of Temperature : It is seen from Table 2 that the value of 'n' decreases with rise of temperature under otherwise identical conditions. This means that there is decrease in association of acid-anion complex. This decrease in association of acid-anion complex will affect the overall acidity of acids in benzene which is clear from the decrease in $\log K_a$ values with rise of temperature (Table 3). Thus like all other acid-base reactions, the reaction between carbinol base of crystal violet and aromatic acid is exothermic. However, it is not possible to get unequivocal values of $-\Delta H$ by the usual plot of $\log K_a$ vs $1/T$, because our K_a involves 'n' which varies with temperature. If this theoretical difficulty is ignored rather high values (20 to 50 Kcal/mole) for $-\Delta H$ are obtained.

The protonation of the carbinol base is kinetically of first order with respect to base but is slightly higher with respect to the aromatic acids³⁰. The values of the catalytic constant k_a are linear with K_a in benzene and with pK_a in water.

One of the authors (G.K.S.) acknowledges with thanks the award of a Senior Research Scholarship from the Ministry of Education, Government of India.

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